

Dental Clinic of Vojvodina

Medical Faculty of Novi Sad

***THE FIRST INTERNATIONAL
SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE
DENTISTRY 2016 NOVI SAD***

PROCEEDINGS

NOVI SAD, 17-th – 19-th May 2016.

***PROCEEDINGS OF
THE FIRST INTERNATIONAL
SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE
DENTISTRY 2016 NOVI SAD***

Publisher: Stylos doo Novi Sad

**Organization of this Conference was approved by
the Scientific Council of the Dental Clinic of Vojvodina**

Editor: Dr Tatjana Puskar, associate professor

CIP classification:

CIP– Каталогизација у публикацији
Библиотека Матице српске, Нови Сад

616.31(082)(048.3)

PROCEEDINGS OF
THE FIRST INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE
DENTISTRY 2016 NOVI SAD, Novi Sad, 17th-19th May 2016. –
Novi Sad: Dental Clinic of Vojvodina, 2016. – CD-ROM; 12cm

Bibliografija uz svaki rad

ISBN 978-86-7473-598-5

a) Стоматологија-Зборници-Апстракти
COBISS.SR-ID 305389063

Message from the President of the Scientific Committee

On behalf of the Organizing and Programme Committee, I'm pleased to welcome you at the First International Scientific Conference Dentistry 2016 Novi Sad. You will be able to attend an interesting scientific programme with well known and respectable speakers from the entire world. They will present contemporary achievements in different fields of dentistry, dental engineering and technology.

We hope you'll enjoy high quality lectures and interesting presentations, followed by stimulating discussions. Apart from the scientific aspect of the conference we wish you to experience the traditional hospitality of Novi Sad and to strengthen the existing friendships and create a lot of new.

We did our best to make this scientific event a great meeting, wishing it to be both informative and enjoyable.

President of the Scientific Committee

Assist. prof. Tatjana Puškar

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BIOMECHANICAL APPROACH IN RESTORATIVE DENTISTRY

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Abstract

The main goal of restorative dentistry is adequate restoration of any loss of hard tooth substance in order to reestablish anatomical and functional features of teeth. Thereby, a key role for the achievement of long-term therapeutic success represents careful planning of the restorative procedure, with special attention focused on the design of cavity preparation and selection of restorative material. While planning, in addition to knowledge of the basic principles of restorative dentistry, biomechanical approach allows recognition of additional parameters that contribute to higher resistance of the remaining dental structures to unfavorable responses from the masticatory forces. This consequently ensures the preservation of the integrity of the tooth-restoration complex.

1. Introduction

In modern restorative dentistry the special importance is given to clinical procedures that favor conservation of hard tooth structure, as one of the most important factors for success of therapeutic procedure [1, 2]. For this reason, the reconstruction of extensive cavities, which are characterized by a significant loss of dental hard tissue, represents a special challenge. The main reason is that the loss of tooth structure from caries, trauma or extensive preparation, leads to a decrease in the resistance of the remaining dental structures to the masticatory forces, thus increasing the risk of fracture of the tooth and/or filling [3-7]. Accordingly, beside the restoration of the tooth morphology, implementation of an adequate restorative procedure aims to preserve the resistance of the remaining dental structures [8-10].

2. The basic principles of biomechanics in restorative dentistry

In oral environment, teeth and restorative materials are exposed to the functional and parafunctional forces. Consequently, changes in the teeth and restorations that are manifesting

in stress and strain occur. Biomechanics is a specific scientific discipline which investigates interaction of these forces with tooth structures and restorative materials, as well as the phenomena of stress and strain [11, 12].

Masticatory forces can operate at any angle and in any direction. Stress however, occurs in only two forms: normal stress and shear stress. Usually it is a combination of both. Since the occurrence of the stress is accompanied with the sequential strain (ϵ), according to the theory of material resistance, strain depends on the stress (Fig. 1) [11, 13].

Fig. 1 Stress-strain curve

As Figure 1 shows, in the initial part of the curve (from point 0 to point A), increase of stress values is followed by the increase of strain, and this change is linearly proportional. In this area, deformation of the material is elastic, meaning that material can achieve its initial shape after the load is removed. Point A represents the elastic limit (σ_e) and it is defined as the maximum stress that a material will withstand without permanent deformation. It represents the boundary between the elastic and plastic deformation of materials. With further increase of the stress, plastic deformation occurs (part of the curve from point A to point C), which sooner or later leads to fracture (σ_k) (point C). The maximum stress that occurs in the material before the onset of a fracture is called ultimate strength (σ_m) (point B). For brittle materials (ceramics), ultimate strength and fracture strength are similar, which is why these materials fracture without large deformation. However, when selecting material for the restoration, elastic limit is more important compared to the ultimate strength, because it determines when a material will start to deform permanently.

In addition to the elastic limit, an important mechanical characteristic of the material is modulus of elasticity or Young's modulus (E), which represents the stiffness of a material in the area of elastic deformation [12]. The elastic properties of the material are determined by the chemical interatomic bonds. The stronger the bond between atoms is the stronger is the force necessary for their separation and deformation of the material. Thus, such a material has a higher modulus of elasticity. Therefore, elasticity of the material is only determined by the chemical structure of the material [11, 13].

3. Biomechanical characteristics of restored teeth

Intact tooth is made up of tissues that have different modulus of elasticity (enamel: 48 to 84.1GPa, dentin: 13.8 to 18.6GPa) [1, 8]. While chewing, biting forces act on the broad surface of the enamel as a compression. Due to its high modulus of elasticity, the occurrence of stress is predominantly localized in the enamel, and only a smaller part of the load is transferred to the dentin, where minimal deformation occurs [4, 12]. However, a restored tooth tends to transfer stress differently, mostly as combination of compression, tension, or shear along the tooth-restoration interface. This phenomenon is especially pronounced in extensive cavities, in which it was found that one-sided loss of the marginal ridge leads to reduced fracture resistance of the teeth by 46%, while preparation of mesio-occluso-distal (MOD) cavity causes a decrease in resistance by more than 60% [3, 7]. Stress and strain in such situations, beside the modulus of elasticity, are determined by the cavity preparation design and type of restorative material [1, 4, 10, 14, 15].

3.1. Influence of cavity preparation design on biomechanical characteristics of restored teeth

Cavity preparation is a mechanical alteration of a tooth damaged by caries or trauma to receive a restorative material, in order to restore the morphological form and function of the teeth. Although the development of dental restorative materials has led to changes in the design of cavity preparation, it is still necessary to respect the basic principles to ensure the success of the therapeutic procedure: 1) complete removal of a tooth structures affected by caries lesion, 2) the inclusion of all weakened walls in preparation 3) forming a cavity shape which under the force of mastication provides adequate resistance form and prevent filling dislocation [16]. However, in addition to the above, the cavity preparation design elements

such as the cavity depth, the isthmus width and the cusp reduction must be especially considered in the planning process of the restoration of teeth, with the aim of achieving optimal biomechanical characteristics of the tooth-restoration complex.

In MOD cavities, cavity depth has the most significant influence on stress distribution [10, 14, 17, 18]. The deeper cavity is, the risk of tooth fracture is higher, which is accompanied with the amount of loss tooth structures. Also, bending moment is higher in deeper cavities favouring breaking of the cavity walls. In contrast to the above mentioned isthmus width which is also determined by the amount of loss tooth structures, showed minimal influence on the biomechanical characteristics of the restored teeth [19-21].

Regarding the cusp reduction, traditionally it is indicated when the isthmus width is greater than 2/3 of intercuspal distance [22]. Recent research, however, showed that the thickness of the cavity walls by itself has no significant influence on the resistance of the tooth. Thus the need for this procedure remains questionable [21, 23]. Additionally, this procedure involves the removal of healthy tooth substance, which is in contrast to the current principles of restorative dentistry. However, from biomechanical point of view, a minimum cusp reduction of 1.5-2.5mm significantly changes stress distribution in the remaining tooth structure while decreasing the stress values [1, 21]. Also, cusp reduction provides the transfer of a load from the filling to the tooth in the form of compressive pressure, as is the case with an intact tooth. So, cusp reduction creates a more favorable distribution of lower stress values within the cavity walls, thus protecting the remaining tooth structures from adverse biomechanical reactions to the masticatory forces. Moreover, this contributes to increased fracture resistance of restored teeth [24].

3.2. Influence of restorative material on biomechanical characteristics of restored teeth

Continuous development and improvement of the characteristics of adhesive systems and composite resin materials, high demands of patients for aesthetic restorations, as well as the confirmed clinical longevity of these materials [25, 26], have contributed to make resin composites currently considered the materials of choice for teeth restoration. Even in cases of extensive cavity reconstruction, where fixed prosthetic could be indicated, preference should be given to conservative restoration with the use of composite resins [2, 27]. It is confirmed that this type of restoration preserves the remaining tooth substance from further preparation, a satisfactory fracture resistance of restored teeth can be accomplished, and time needed to

carry out therapeutic procedure is shorter [7-10, 28, 29]. However, due to the problem of polymerization shrinkage and subsequent appearance of stress and strain within the dental tissues; indirect composite and ceramic restorations were suggested as better solution for the restoration of extensive cavities.

The above mentioned restorative materials have different biomechanical characteristics, especially Young's modulus of elasticity. Ceramic materials have the greatest modulus of elasticity (about 90GPa) which makes them extremely rigid. Because of that, even if high stress occurs, it will display a little deformation, thus protecting the remaining tooth structure from fracture. In addition, due to its brittleness the risk of tooth fracture is minimized because the restorative material is likely to fracture before the tooth, preserving such a tooth for new restoration. Conversely, composite resins are more flexible (modulus of elasticity about 6GPa for direct restoration and 50GPa for indirect restoration). Thus, more occlusal force is transferred to the remaining tooth structure providing the higher stress and increasing the risk of unfavourable tooth fracture [3, 15].

4. Conclusions

Although modern restorative dentistry favors maximum preservation of healthy tooth substance; biomechanical approach to the restorative procedures has shown that the cusp reduction included in cavity preparation design and the use of restorative materials with higher modulus of elasticity, significantly contributes to the preservation of integrity of the remaining tooth structures, as well as achieving optimal biomechanical characteristics of the tooth-restoration complex.

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